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A pancreaticopleural fistula complicated by the rupture of pancreatic pseudocyst during treatment.

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Abstract

Background: Pancreaticopleural fistulas are a rare complication of acute and chronic pancreatitis. The chronic pancreatitis leading to pancreaticopleural fistulas is often alcoholic in origin; gallstones, trauma, idiopathic pancreatitis and pancreatic duct anomalies are rare causes. Optimal treatment strategies have been medical management with exocrine suppression with octreotide and endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography stenting of the fistulous pancreatic duct. Surgery is necessary when medical and endoscopic management fails, or the underlying condition requires it.

Case presentation: A 60-year-old male reported nonproductive cough, dyspnea, left-sided chest pain, abdominal fullness. Left-sided massive pleural effusion, and a pancreatic cyst attached to left diaphragm and associated with pleura at the paramedian level were detected on abdomino-thoracic computed tomography (CT). Conservative management was planned. During treatment the patient underwent an emergency operation, and rupture of the pancreatic pseudocyst was seen. A cholecystectomy, abdominal lavage and external drainage were performed. Two months later, he was re-admitted to the hospital with complaints of fever, weakness and loss of appetite. Abdomino-thoracic CT showed an abdominal collection located between the pancreatic tail and posterior of the gastric corpus and a cystic lesion in the corpus of the pancreas. The peripancreatic collection was drained using percutaneous drainage, and an endoscopic cystogastrostomy and a stent insertion were performed.

Conclusion: Pancreaticopleural fistulas may be complicated by pseudocyst rupture, but the persistence of pseudocysts after drainage of the ruptured pseudocysts make the procedure more complicated. Endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS)-guided cystogastrostomy and a stent insertion, combined with drainage of the abdominal cavity by a percutaneous catheter may be used for persistent pseudocyst.

Keywords: Pancreaticopleural fistula, pancreatic pseudocyst, rupture, treatment, EUS-guided cystogastrostomy

Introduction

Pancreatic pseudocysts are well-known complications of acute and chronic pancreatitis caused by pancreatic ductal disruption following increased pancreatic ductal pressure, due to stenosis, calculi or protein plugs obstructing the main pancreatic ductal system, or as a result of pancreatic necrosis following an attack of acute pancreatitis. The incidence of pancreatic pseudocysts ranges from 2–10% in acute pancreatitis and 10–30% in chronic pancreatitis^[1,2]. Anterior disruption of a pancreatic duct or a pseudocyst leads to leakage of pancreatic secretions in the free peritoneal cavity, leading to pancreatic ascites. If the pancreatic duct is disrupted posteriorly, the secretions leak through the retroperitoneum into the mediastinum via the aortic or esophageal hiatus and form a pancreaticopleural fistula or manifest themselves as mediastinal pseudocysts. These pseudocysts rupture into the pleural cavity to form a pancreaticopleural fistula. Pancreaticopleural fistulas are a rare complication of pancreatitis seen in 0.4% of patients with pancreatitis and 4.5% of patients with pancreatic pseudocysts. The chronic pancreatitis leading to pancreaticopleural fistulas is typically alcoholic in origin;

gallstones, trauma, idiopathic pancreatitis and pancreatic duct anomalies are rare causes^[3].

Pleural effusions due to pancreaticopleural fistulas are predominately left-sided, but are right-sided in 19% of cases and bilateral in 14% of cases^[4]. Diagnosis, ranging from 12–49 days, is often delayed because symptoms are associated with pulmonary complications, which is a critical issue. Suspicion is necessary for patients with a history of acute pancreatitis and alcohol abuse presenting with pleural effusions that recur after thoracentesis and for which there is no obvious other cause. An elevated pleural fluid amylase level (> 1,000 U/L), with mean amylase levels above 10,000 U/L (13,000–53,000 U/L) is an important diagnostic tool given pancreaticopleural fistulas. The pleural fluid protein level is also high (>30 gr/L) due to chronic inflammation of the pleural surface. The serum amylase is typically elevated as well, secondary to the resorption of amylase from the pleural surface.

Although it provides limited information, posteroanterior (PA) chest radiography is the first line of investigation. An endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) used to be the preferred investigation for confirming the diagnosis of pancreaticopleural fistula with

an sensitivity of 78%. Despite its risk of complications (pancreatitis, infection, bleeding, perforation), ERCP has been widely used due to the advantages of endoscopic treatments. Although the sensitivity of computed tomography (CT) in the diagnosis of pancreaticopleural fistula (47%) is lower than the sensitivity of ERCP, it is the gold standard for investigating pleural effusion. CT also detects abdominal abnormalities associated with pancreatic pathologies such as pseudocysts. Magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography is a noninvasive alternative to ERCP and useful for demonstrating pancreatic pathologies and fistulas with a sensitivity of 80%. It is also useful for severe pancreatic strictures where ERCP is not suitable^[3-5].

We present the diagnosis and treatment of a pancreaticopleural fistula caused by pancreatic pseudocysts developed from acute biliary pancreatitis.

Case report

A 60-year-old male reported nonproductive cough, dyspnea, left-sided chest pain, abdominal fullness, nausea, vomiting, decreased appetite and weight loss. He never drank but smoked 40 packs of cigarettes per year. He had a history of treatment for acute biliary pancreatitis 6 months ago.

A palpable left-upper quadrant abdominal mass and diminished breath sounds on the left side were detected; there were no jaundice or fever. Cardiovascular and neurological examinations were normal. Left-sided pleural effusion was seen on an PA chest radiography. Serohemorrhagic fluid was obtained by thoracentesis. Pleural fluid has the following characteristics; amylase 13830 [normal <1000 U/L], total protein 50 [normal <30 g/L], erythrocyte $500 \times 10^6/L$, leucocyte $<25 \times 10^6/L$ and no bacteria. Blood test has the following characteristics; wbc $8,72 \times 10^9/L$ [normal $<10 \times 10^9/L$], alkaline phosphatase 201 [normal <120 U/L], γ GT 42 [normal <49 U/L], LDH 306 [normal <232 U/L], bilirubin 0,5 [normal <1,1 mg/dL], amylase 464 [normal <220 U/L], CRP 38 [normal <5 mg/dL].

Abdominal sonography revealed millimetric stones and sludge in the gallbladder and a 17×13 cm cystic lesion in the pancreatic tail and corpus. Left-sided massive pleural effusion, perisplenic fluid and a 10.5×13.3×17.0 cm pancreatic cyst attached to left diaphragm and associated with pleura at the paramedian level were detected on abdomino-thoracic CT (Figure 1). Pleural fluid was drained (3600 cc), and the pulmonary symptoms of the patient decreased. The patient's oral intake was restricted and nutrition was maintained by total parenteral nutrition in conjunction with the subcutaneous use of long-acting somatostatin analogues (octreotide acetate 100 μ g, 3 times a day). Conservative management with pancreatic duct stenting was planned, but 8 days after the insertion of the intercostal drain the patient reported severe abdominal pain, fever and leukocytosis ($19 \times 10^9/L$). An emergency operation was performed, and rupture of the pancreatic pseudocyst was seen. A cholecystectomy (for gallstones), abdominal lavage and external drainage were performed; the intercostal drain was withdrawn 2 days after surgery, and the patient was discharged from the intensive care

unit. After 2 weeks of treatment, he was discharged from the hospital without any problems. Two months later, he was re-admitted to the hospital with complaints of fever, weakness and loss of appetite. Abdomino-thoracic CT showed 60×20 mm abdominal collection located between the pancreatic tail and posterior of the gastric corpus and a 97×45 cm cystic lesion in the corpus of the pancreas. There was no pleural effusion. The peripancreatic collection was drained using percutaneous drainage, and an endoscopic cystogastrostomy and a stent insertion were performed. The patient's nutrition was maintained by total parenteral nutrition with the use of somatostatin analogues for 6 weeks. Four months later, there was neither pleural effusion nor pancreatic pseudocysts but only a cystogastric stent image on the control abdomino-thoracic CT (Figure 2). He has no any complaint. Amylase level was in normal range.

Figure 1. Coronal image clearly shows fistula formation between pseudocyst and pleura (Gray-white gradient arrow).

Figure 2. Coronal and sagittal reformatted CT images of the pseudocyst after treatment with endoscopic cystogastrostomy and gastric stenting.

Discussion

Pancreaticopleural fistulas are typically seen in male patients between the ages of 20 and 60. Pleural effusions due to pancreaticopleural fistulas are predominantly left-sided, and the diagnosis is often delayed because symptoms are associated with pulmonary complications (dyspnea, cough, chest pain, etc.). Abdominal pain is rarely reported^[4-7]. Clinical presentation in this case was typical for pancreaticopleural fistulas. The patient had a history of

treatment for acute biliary pancreatitis 6 months ago, and he had predominantly respiratory symptoms related to pleural effusion. After detecting pleural effusion on the PA chest radiograph, an abdomino-thoracic CT was taken and thoracentesis was performed.

There have been no systematic studies evaluating the optimal management of pancreaticopleural fistulas. Three types of treatment modalities are used:

(1) Medical management (intercostal drainage, inhibition of oral intake, total parenteral nutrition and octreotide use): The production of pancreatic enzymes is suppressed by inhibition of oral intake in conjunction with the use of long-acting somatostatin analogues. This treatment is continued for 2–4 weeks, and the patient is observed for improvement. Resolution of pancreaticopleural fistulas was reported in 31–65% of adult cases. Endoscopic or surgical treatment is a last resort^[3,5,7,8].

(2) ERCP with or without endoscopic pancreatic stent placement: ERCP identifies pancreatic duct strictures and stones downstream from the fistula, which can be treated using papillary sphincterotomy, balloon dilatation, extraction of stones from the main pancreatic duct or stent replacement. The optimal duration of endoscopic drainage is unknown. Many cases may still require surgery, particularly for recurrent fluid collections secondary to stenosis or disruption of the main pancreatic duct resulting from the stent^[3,5].

(3) Surgery is necessary when medical and endoscopic management fails or when the underlying condition requires surgical intervention. Pancreatic resection or enteropancreatic anastomosis to the site of pancreatic duct leakage or to the pseudocyst (cystogastrostomy, cystojejunostomy, etc.) may be conducted^[5].

Signs and symptoms of pancreatic pseudocyst rupture vary from mild to severe depending on where the rupture occurs. Spontaneous rupture of the pancreatic pseudocyst into the surrounding peritoneal cavity causes peritonitis, leading to hemorrhagic shock, and requires emergency surgical exploration. Although the drainage of pancreatic pseudocysts is preferably internal, external drainage may be selected^[9].

Pancreatic pseudocysts are classified based on their relationship to the omentum majus. Pseudocysts within the omentum majus often include a common wall with the gastrointestinal tract. Retroperitoneal perforations of the pseudocysts adjacent to the stomach are rare. In these types of pseudocysts, endoscopic ultrasonography (EUS)-guided drainage can be performed successfully. To date, it is believed that EUS-guided drainage is useful only for pseudocysts to adhere to gastric walls. However, according to Nan and colleagues, it is possible to use EUS-guided drainage (combined with drainage of the abdominal cavity by a nasobiliary catheter) for pancreatic pseudocysts that do not adhere to gastric walls^[10]. In this case, EUS-guided cystogastrostomy (not combined with drainage of the abdominal cavity by a nasobiliary catheter, but instead using a percutaneous catheter) and a stent insertion was used for a pancreatic pseudocysts without adherence to

gastric wall. Four months later, there was neither pleural effusion nor pancreatic pseudocysts.

Conclusion

Pancreaticopleural fistulas are most commonly caused by disruption of the pancreatic duct due to chronic pancreatitis; they may also be caused by leakage from a pancreatic pseudocyst. Pancreaticopleural fistulas may be complicated by pseudocyst rupture, and the persistence of pseudocysts after drainage of the ruptured pseudocysts may complicate procedures. In this case, management of the pancreaticopleural fistula was complicated by the rupture of pancreatic pseudocysts. EUS-guided cystogastrostomy (combined with drainage of the abdominal cavity by a percutaneous catheter) and a stent insertion may be used for persistent pseudocysts that do not adhere to gastric walls.

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